

SI02. Demographic parameters of the questionnaire respondents

The age group between 30-39 predominated in the responses, i.e. people who are in the middle of active professional and research life. In terms of gender identity, there was a slight preponderance of males (57.5%), with a not inconsiderable proportion of females (37.5%), as well as some gender variant or refused responses (and one joker). The majority have a PhD degree (62.8%), some have a Master's degree (28.9%), and fewer have a Bachelor's degree or habilitation. The majority work in academia (70.2%), with students making up another large proportion (9.9%). Heritage management, museums and commercial archaeology were each represented by only around 3%.

In terms of geographical distribution, there is a clear preponderance of responses from Germany, followed by the United Kingdom, Denmark, the Czech Republic and the United States of America. Other mainly European countries were relatively evenly represented with less than 5 responses. The geographical dominance of Germany, however, is most likely biased by the strong dissemination of the questionnaire through German-speaking archaeology networks and does not necessarily represent a major German research interest in computational archaeology.

In the self-description, most of those participating in the survey considered themselves rather familiar with the use of computational methods (78.5 %) and connecting to current theoretical debates (77.7 %). Just under half (48.8 %) had attended a specific conference on computational archaeology (such as CAA) in the last 5 years, and 37.2 % had attended one on theoretical archaeology (such as TAG). The vast majority also attended one of the larger general conferences (such as EAA, SAA, UISPP, etc.) during this period.